

“A prospective comparative study between hemorrhoidopexy and open hemorrhoidectomy”

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Abstract: -

AIM- The aim of topic is to compare hemorrhoidopexy with open hemorrhoidectomy in the management of hemorrhoids with reference to complication like pain, retention of urine, bleeding and anal incontinence, comforts to the patient, intra operative complications, and hospital stay.

- **MATERIALS AND METHOD** - "After receiving approval from the institutional ethics committee, a prospective examination commenced..." This Prospective study will be carried out on 60 patients who presented to the OPD and emergency department of surgery in PIMS. Between June 2023 and May 2024, a total of 60 patients diagnosed with grade III hemorrhoids were randomly allocated to either undergo transanal suture rectopexy/ haemorrhoidopexy (n=30) or the Milligan Morgan procedure (n=30). Outcome evaluation was conducted at multiple time points: 24 hours, 3 weeks, 6 weeks, and 3 months postoperatively, focusing on variables such as post-operative complications and symptom resolution.
- **RESULT-** Comparison between the two procedures revealed significant differences in mean operating time, intra-operative and post-operative bleeding, postoperative pain levels, analgesic usage, and duration of hospital stay. Notably, transanal suture rectopexy demonstrated superiority over open hemorrhoidectomy in terms of intraoperative bleeding, postoperative pain management, shorter hospital stays, and lower rates of postoperative recurrence during the Three -month follow-up period.
- **Conclusion-** "Transanal suture rectopexy stands out for its reduced incidence of postoperative complications and improved patient compliance compared to the Milligan Morgan open hemorrhoidectomy."

Keywords: Chivate's procedure/Transanal suture rectopexy [TR]/ haemorrhoidopexy, Milligan-Morgan/Open hemorrhoidectomy [OH], Post operative Pain.

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INTRODUCTION-

Hemorrhoids, characterized by enlarged blood vessels and tissue in the lower rectum or around the anus, involve the downward displacement of anal cushions containing arteriovenous anastomoses.

Hemorrhoids, characterized by the enlargement and descent of anal cushions, commonly cause rectal bleeding and are associated with factors such as straining during bowel movements, prolonged sitting, heavy lifting, obesity, and intense coughing, affecting approximately half of the population by age 50, with a prevalence of about 5% at any given time.¹

Hemorrhoids, found in the anal canal's three main columns, are categorized as internal or external based on their location relative to the dentate line. Internal hemorrhoids are graded I to IV according to prolapse severity for treatment customization, often presenting symptoms like painless bleeding, anal itching, pain, and tissue prolapse resembling grapes. External hemorrhoids are typically asymptomatic unless thrombosed, causing severe pain due to their innervation by somatic nerves.^{2,3,4}

Grade I hemorrhoids minimally prolapse and may become trapped by anal sphincter closure, leading to occasional discomfort and bleeding with straining. Grade II hemorrhoids protrude further into

the mucosa, causing a noticeable lump that typically resolves after defecation, unless thrombosis occurs. Grade III hemorrhoids, indicative of chronic disease, often require manual replacement due to persistent prolapse causing anal sphincter dilation. Grade IV hemorrhoids, also called prolapsed piles, are permanently external, with distension of the dentate line and redundant perianal skin.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of topic is to compare hemorrhoidopexy with open hemorrhoidectomy in the management of hemorrhoids with reference to complication like pain, retention of urine, bleeding and anal incontinence, comforts to the patient, intra operative complications, and hospital stay.

Objectives-

- To compare the outcome of hemorrhoidopexy with open hemorrhoidectomy in terms of
- Duration of surgery,
- post-operative pain, bleeding and urinary retention
- Recovery period
- Duration of hospital stay.

METHOD-

After receiving approval from the institutional ethics committee, a prospective examination commenced..." This Prospective study will be carried out on 60 patients who presented to the OPD and emergency department of surgery in PIMS umarda Udaipur . Between June 2023 and May 2024, a total of 60 patients diagnosed with grade III hemorrhoids were randomly allocated to either undergo haemorrhoidopexy (n=30) or the Milligan Morgan procedure (n=30).

Inclusion criteria

- Age between 20-60 years
- Both Male and Females
- All patients with symptomatic hemorrhoid grades III (pain, bleeding and discomfort defecation)
- Third degree internal Haemorrhoids
- Recurrent hemorrhoids after surgery.

Exclusion criteria

- All patient with grade I , II , IV Hemorrhoid
- Associated Fissure- in- ano
- Associated Fistula -in -ano
- Previous perianal surgeries
- Patient with forth degree hemorrhoids

PROCEDURE and TECHNIQUE:

TRADITIONAL / OPEN HAEMORRHOIDECTOMY TECHNIQUE

Under either general or spinal anesthesia, patients are positioned in lithotomy, and the anal sphincter is gently stretched to prolapse internal hemorrhoids. Each hemorrhoid is grasped with forceps, and traction is applied, forming a triangle with paired hemostats. A V-shaped incision is made on either side of the hemorrhoid, exposing the lower border of the internal sphincter. Transfixing Vicryl ligatures are applied, and hemorrhoids are excised 1.25 cm above the ligature. Wounds are trimmed, subcutaneous arteries secured, and petroleum jelly gauze inserted into the anus to cover exposed areas. Complications may include pain, hemorrhage, anal stenosis, fissures, abscesses, fistulas, and long-term incontinence.

FIGURE- 1

FIGURE-2

CHIVATE SUTURE HAEMORRHOIDOPEXY TECHNIQUE

The procedure began with patients receiving P.C. Enema in the evening 12 hours and 6 hours before the surgery to ensure optimal bowel preparation. Subsequently, under spinal anesthesia, patients were positioned in lithotomy with a slight downward tilt of the head, which effectively reduced the prolapsing pile masses, facilitating easier access to the anal canal.

Once positioned, the lax mucosal and submucosal tissues were carefully repositioned to their anatomical alignment. To aid in patient comfort and ease of instrument insertion, the anal canal was lubricated with xylocaine jelly. A specialized self-illuminated proctoscope with a sliding valve, ingeniously designed by Dr. Chivate, was then utilized. This device allowed for clear visualization of the anal canal and identification of the dentate line.

Upon identifying the dentate line, meticulous suturing commenced. Two circumferential suture lines were placed, positioned 2cm and 4cm proximal to the dentate line, respectively. The initial stitch was tied securely, followed by subsequent stitches measuring 0.5-1 cm in length, which were double interlocked. This technique effectively prevented the purse string effect and minimized the risk of anal stenosis. Careful attention was paid to ensure that the sutures did not penetrate the full thickness of the rectal wall.

By positioning both suture lines above the dentate line, in the insensitive part of the anal canal, postoperative pain was minimized. A 2-0 polyglactin with a round body 30 mm ½ needle was used for suturing. Following the completion of suturing, the lax mucosa and submucosa were restored to their original position. To prevent recurrence, the blood supply to the hemorrhoidal plexus was carefully interrupted at two points, reducing the likelihood of collateral formation. This comprehensive approach aimed to address both the immediate surgical needs and long-term outcomes of the patients undergoing hemorrhoidectomy.

FIGURE- 3

FIGURE- 4

FIGURE- 5

RESULT AND DISCUSSION –

For this study, the diagnosed patients evaluated for surgical and anaesthetic fitness .Then they were admitted in surgical unit concerned at Pims Hospital umarda during the period of June 2023 to may-2024

After in formed consent, Both male and female in the age group between 20 years and 60 years subjected for elective surgery or both the methods , selected at a random basis.

About 30 cases of open hemorrhoidectomy and 30 cases of hemorrhoidopexy are included in this study.

The patients in the postoperative ward give analgesic in the form of injections, adequate sedation on the day of surgery , liquid diet after 6 hours , normal diet from night , stool softeners and sitz bath.

A total of 60 patients were enrolled in the study, with 30 individuals allocated to each group. The mean age of the participants predominantly fell within the range of 40-50 years. The majority of cases comprised males, with 11 females and 19 males in the open hemorrhoidectomy group, and 7 females and 23 males in the Chivta hemorrhoidopexy group. The minor variation in sex distribution between the two groups was determined to be statistically insignificant (p=0.57).

YEARS	NO. OF PATIENTS
25-35 YEARS	7
35-45 YEARS	22
45-60 YEARS	31
TOTAL	60

TABLE 1 – AGE DISTRIBUTION

GRAPH - 1

GENDER	OH	SH	P – VALUE
MALE	19	23	0.5
FEMALE	11	7	
TOTAL	30	30	

TABLE 2– GENDER DISTRIBUTION

GRAPH 2

Our study findings indicate that the mean duration of operation time for open hemorrhoidectomy was 35 minutes with a standard deviation of 5 minutes, whereas for suture hemorrhoidopexy, it was 40 minutes with a standard deviation of 8 minutes. The difference between the two groups was found to be statistically significant with a p-value of < 0.001. This implies that the open hemorrhoidectomy procedure required less time compared to suture hemorrhoidopexy. This statistical significance suggests that the observed difference in operation time between the two procedures is unlikely due to random chance alone, strengthening the reliability of our findings.

TABLE -3

OH	SH	P -VALUE
32+/- 5 MINUTE	40 +/- 8 MINUTE	<0.001

Early postoperative complications, including pain, bleeding, and urinary retention, were observed following hemorrhoid surgery. Out of the total cohort, 41% of patients reported postoperative pain, with 30% in the open hemorrhoidectomy group and 11.6% in the suture hemorrhoidopexy group. The incidence of postoperative bleeding was 28.3%, with 21.6% in the open hemorrhoidectomy group and 6.6% in the hemorrhoidopexy group. Additionally, urinary retention affected 20 patients, with 21% in the open hemorrhoidectomy group and 11.6% in the hemorrhoidopexy group. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the two surgical approaches for pain (p<0.001) and bleeding (p<0.001), while urinary retention showed a trend toward significance (p<0.071). Management of these complications primarily involved conservative measures such as local packs and catheterization. These findings underscore the importance of considering both the efficacy and potential complications of different surgical techniques in hemorrhoid treatment.

TABLE -4

PAIN	OH	SH	TOTAL	P- VALUE
YES	18	7	25	<0.001
NO	9	26	35	
BLEEDING	OH	SH	TOTAL	P-VALUE
YES	13	4	17	0.001
NO	15	28	43	
URINARY RETENTION	OH	SH	TOTAL	P- VALUE
YES	13	7	20	0.071
NO	17	23	40	

GRAPH-3

Patients undergoing suture hemorrhoidopexy experienced a significantly shorter mean duration of hospital stay (2.33 ± 0.47 days) compared to those undergoing open hemorrhoidectomy (3.43 ± 0.62 days), with a p-value of <0.001 . Similarly, the time for return to work was markedly shorter in the suture group (6 days) compared to the open group (11 days), also demonstrating statistical significance with a p-value of <0.001 . These findings highlight the advantages of suture hemorrhoidopexy in terms of faster recovery and earlier return to daily activities compared to traditional open hemorrhoidectomy.

POST OPERATIVE HOSPITAL STAY

OH	SH	P- VALUE
3 DAYS	2+/-1 DAY	<0.001

RETURN TO WORK

OH	SH	P- VALUE
9 DAYS	6 DAYS	<0.001

At the 3-week follow-up, the open surgery group exhibited a higher incidence of pain (26%) compared to the hemorrhoidopexy group (3.3%). Additionally, bleeding per rectum during defecation was more prevalent in the open surgery group (10%) compared to the hemorrhoidopexy group (3.3%), as was constipation (20% vs. 6.6%, respectively). However, no residual incontinence was observed in either group.

At the 6-week follow-up, although pain persisted in both groups, it was less prevalent in the hemorrhoidopexy group (3.3% vs. 16% in the open surgery group). Bleeding per rectum during defecation was reported by a similar percentage of patients in both groups (3.3%). Constipation was also less common in the hemorrhoidopexy group (3% vs. 6% in the open surgery group). By the 3rd month follow-up, neither group exhibited persistent pain, bleeding, constipation, or incontinence.

CONCLUSION

In our 24-month study comparing open haemorrhoidectomy with transanal suture haemorrhoidopexy, we found significant advantages with the latter technique. Transanal suture haemorrhoidopexy showed reduced post-operative pain, lower analgesic requirement, fewer complications, shorter hospital stays,

and quicker return to normal activities. These findings support its wider adoption as a safer and more cost-effective option for haemorrhoid treatment. Additionally, our study suggests its feasibility in rural healthcare settings, potentially improving care accessibility. Overall, transanal suture haemorrhoidopexy emerges as a promising alternative to open haemorrhoidectomy, emphasizing better patient outcomes and healthcare efficiency.

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